

1. Open Research Fund application

Reference number	214475/Z/18/Z
Applicant name	Dr Darren Dahly
Title of application	Embedding FAIR principles into analysis workflows with data packaging: Costs and best practices
Total amount requested	€50,854.00

2. Application summary

Application title
Embedding FAIR principles into analysis workflows with data packaging: Costs and best practices

Proposed duration of funding (months, this should be no longer than 1 year)
12

Proposed start date	04/02/2019
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Is your application being submitted through a university?	Yes
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Name of administering organisation
University College Cork

Lead applicant's address at administering organisation	
Department/Division	College of Medicine and Health
Organisation	University College Cork
Street	Western Road
City/Town	Cork
Postcode/Zipcode	00000
Country	Ireland

Research funding area
Please select from the drop-down list the funding area that you consider your research falls under
Population and Public Health

3. Lead applicant

Lead applicant details	
Full Name	Dr Darren Dahly
Department	Clinical Research Facility Cork
Division	
Organisation	University College Cork
Address Line 1	Western Gateway Building, 4.23. Western Road.
City/Town	Cork
Postcode	00000
Country	Ireland
Telephone No.	
Email Address	ddahly@ucc.ie

ORCID iD	
ORCID iD	0000-0003-0110-324X

Career history (current/most recent first)			
From	To	Position	Organisation
08/2015	-	Senior Lecturer in Patient Focused Research Methods	University College Cork
08/2013	07/2015	Senior Postdoctoral Research Fellow	University College Cork
08/2008	07/2013	Lecturer in Epidemiology	University of Leeds
05/2002	05/2003	Field Epidemiologist	Population Services International

Education/training				
From	To	Qualification	Subject	Organisation
08/2003	07/2009	Doctor of Philosophy (PhD;DPhil)	Epidemiology (Nutrition)	University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
08/2001	07/2003	Master of Science (MSc)	International Health	Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health
08/1998	06/2001	Bachelor of Arts (BA)	Biology	Hendrix College (Conway, Arkansas, USA)

Source(s) of personal salary support
University College Cork

Clinical status	
Do you have a medical/veterinary degree?	No

Career breaks	
Have you had any career breaks or periods of part-time work, for example	No

parental or long-term sick leave?	
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Do you wish to undertake this award part time?	No
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Career contributions
What are your most important research-related contributions to date? This may include contributions to health policy or practice, or to technology or product discovery and development.

My research career contributions to date can be roughly divided into two areas. The first is in the area of infant growth and its potential impact on lifelong health. Working with data from the Cebu Longitudinal Health and Nutrition Survey, my research demonstrated that urban development in a lower income context can influence obesity risk, and identified how maternal constraint of fetal growth can exacerbate these risks. I did similar work with the COHORTS collaboration, contributing to a number of important papers demonstrating the degree to which a poor nutritional environment in early life deleteriously impacts lifelong health, as well as other social and economic factors. During this period of research, I developed an interest in latent variable statistical methods, particularly growth mixture models. This work led to a MRC Population Health Scientist fellowship to study patterns of infant growth and their relationship to later health using growth mixture models, which has led to better understanding of the limits of these models. My expertise in this area is reflected in my service as a statistics editor for the *Journal of the Developmental Origins of Health and Disease*, and for *Longitudinal and Life Course Studies*.

Over time, I developed deeper skills in statistical modelling and brought that expertise to other research areas. This eventually contributed to my appointment as a Senior Lecturer in Research Methods at UCC, where I am the Principal Statistician for the HRB CRF-C. I now provide statistical and data expertise through collaboration to a variety of patient-focused research projects (while still dedicating about 10% of my time to studies of infant growth). Doing this work has opened my eyes to an important systemic challenge in science, which is the general lack of data skills among investigators. I believe this substantially contributes to the issues we are seeing with respect to research integrity and reproducibility. Consequently, I am now developing a meta-research program in open science and statistical consulting to understand how we can best support researchers.

Research outputs
List up to 5 of your most significant research outputs, ensuring that at least two of these are from the last five years. Provide a statement describing their significance and your contribution (up to 50 words per output).

Research outputs may include (but are not limited to):

- Peer-reviewed publications and preprints
- Datasets, software and research materials
- Inventions, patents and commercial activity

For original research publications please indicate those arising from Wellcome-funded grants in **bold**, and provide the PubMed Central ID (PMCID) reference for each of these. Please refer to guidance notes.

Publications should be in chronological order with the most recent first. Please give citation in full, including title of paper and all authors. Citations to preprints should state "Preprint", the repository name and the articles persistent identifier (e.g DOI).*

*(*All authors, unless more than 10, in which case please use 'et al', ensuring that your position as author remains clear.)*

1. Dahly DL, Smith HA, Kearney PM. Systematic review of infant body composition (0 - 2 years of age) - *Open Science Framework Project* (<https://osf.io/xn98q/>). The project currently includes a preprint of the review, the complete dataset used in the review, the R scripts used to analyse the

data, including a RMarkdown files that reproduces the results section of the review.

The review evidences important gaps in knowledge about infant body composition, which has implications for infant health-monitoring and research on the early life origins of obesity and other NCDs. I led the research, designed the review, conducted the analysis, and supervised the data collection for this review.

2. Caplice NM, DeVoe M, Choi J, Dahly DL, et al. (2018) Randomized placebo controlled trial evaluating the safety and efficacy of single low dose intracoronary insulin like growth factor following percutaneous coronary intervention in acute myocardial infarction (RESUS-AMI). American Heart Journal, 200: 110-117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ahj.2018.03.018> PMID:29898838

I was the Trial Statistician for RESUS-AMI, a feasibility study of treating cardiac patients with a single low dose of IGF after PCI to see if this improves heart remodelling following infarction. I was responsible for the data analysis, and we are now designing the definitive trial.

3. Lavan A, Eustace J, Dahly DL, et al. (2017) Incident adverse drug reactions in geriatric inpatients: a multicentred observational study. Therapeutic Advances in Drug Safety, 9(1):13-23. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2042098617736191> PMID:29318003

I was the Trial Statistician for SENATOR, an ongoing, international clinical trial of software aimed at reducing adverse drug reactions in elderly patients. I substantially contributed to the design of the trial, and am responsible for all resulting data analyses (except the economic evaluation).

4. Dahly DL, Li X, Smith HA, Khashan AS, Murray DM, Kiely ME, O'B Hourihane J, McCarthy FP, Kenny LC, Kearney PM (2017) Associations between maternal lifestyle factors and neonatal body composition in the Screening for Pregnancy Endpoints (Cork) cohort study. International Journal of Epidemiology, 1;47(1):131-145. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyx221> PMID:29136159

This paper demonstrates potentially important associations between maternal lifestyle factors and the fat and fat-free mass of their offspring. It is a secondary analysis of the SCOPE cohort study. I was the person primarily responsible for the design and conduct of the analysis and writing the paper.

5. **Adair LS, Fall CHD, Osmond C, Stein AD, Martorell R, Ramirez-Zea M, Sachdev HS, Dahly DL, Bas I, Norris S, Mickelsfield L, Hallal P, Victora C. (2013) Associations of linear growth and relative weight gain during early life with adult health and human capital in countries of low and middle income: findings from five birth cohort studies. Lancet. 382(9891):525-34. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(13\)60103-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(13)60103-8). PMID:23541370**

This paper is from the COHORTS collaboration, which was a Wellcome Trust funded study of birth cohorts from lower and middle income countries. I contributed expertise in statistical modelling. I am a named author on several COHORTS publications (and included as a group author of the others).

Principles of open research

Briefly outline how you have embraced and adopted the principles of open research during your career to date

The open science practice I have most embraced is **reproducible programming**, using R and RStudio. Reproducible programming is at the core of our SDAU workflows, we give regular workshops on it (for which were recently awarded a teaching grant), and I have been previously invited to speak on its value (<https://youtu.be/yF3OO15CijU>).

I advocate for open science on social media, including Twitter (@statsepi) and blogging (<https://darrendahly.github.io/>). Relevant blog posts include:

- [Your science is justified by the question, not the answer](#) (03-2017)
- [The perils of exploratory data analysis](#) (02-2017)
- [Why share the data?](#) (06-2015)
- [How can we fix scientific publishing?](#) (02-2012)

I am a leader in open science at my university. I organized a symposium on research integrity at UCC (October 2017), which we are now following up with a three day [Open Science @UCC](#) event in October 2018, featuring international experts in open science and reproducibility, including Profs Marcus Munafo (University of Bristol) and Malcolm Macleod (University of Edinburgh). I organise the [Open Science Challenge at UCC](#) (<https://crfcsdau.github.io/post/>) where researchers come to learn about different open science tools from one another.

4. Team members and collaborators

Will you require any team members or key collaborators for this proposal?

Yes

Please list your team members or key collaborators (name and organisation) and provide a very brief outline of their role in the proposed research.

Eoghan Ó Carragáin, Head of Research and Digital Services, University College Cork Library. (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8131-2150>)

Eoghan leads the Research and Digital Services unit in UCC Library with responsibility for supporting Open Access and FAIR Data Stewardship across campus. He is passionate about making data stewardship work in practice for researchers across all domains. He currently chairs the Infrastructure Working Group of Ireland's *National Open Research Forum*. He previously worked at the National Library of Ireland, where he led a team of software engineers in developing a large-scale digitisation workflow and digital repository infrastructure. In this role he regularly contributed to Open Source software projects, and developed a deep knowledge of digital preservation and data modelling, including considerable experience of working with w3c Linked Data technologies. Eoghan is an active member of the Research Data Alliance contributing, for example, to the final recommendation of the Research Data Repository Interoperability WG (<https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00025>) and initiating a Research Data Packaging working group (<https://rd-alliance.org/approaches-research-data-packaging-rda-11th-plenary-bof-meeting>). He is a member of the Programme Committee for the forthcoming Research Objects 2018 Workshop at the IEEE eScience conference (<http://www.researchobject.org/ro2018/>). With a view to the future, Eoghan is also working on the application of emerging decentralised, peer2peer, and content-addressed storage protocols (e.g. IPFS, DAT) to the area of FAIR Data Stewardship (<https://ti.to/damahub/decentralised-data-infrastructure-for-science>). For this project, he will provide expert advice, help with training and evaluation, and liaise with external collaborators.

Brendan Palmer PhD, Associate Biostatistician, HRB Clinical Research Facility - Cork. (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6637-0723>)

As Associate Biostatistician in the SDAU, Brendan is responsible for the statistical input on a number of studies we support. Working with the Principal Statistician, Brendan helps to design

SDAU workflows for data analysis. He also conducts regular training for researchers looking to incorporate reproducible workflows into their research through the R programming language (<https://github.com/bapalmer/SDAU-Spring-2018>). In 2018 Brendan received a Teaching & Learning Enhancement award by UCC to further develop these workshops. He, along with Eoghan O Carragáin, have recently completed a HRB funded FAIR Data Stewardship course at the GOFAIR offices in Leiden, The Netherlands. For this project, he will help train and supervise a Research Data Coordinator, on both FAIR data and our existing workflows, and then supervise that persons work over the course of this project.

Liam Ramsell - Financial Analyst, HRB CRF-C

Liam will provide expert input on the costing of FAIR data activities. Liam has over 20+ years of Accounting and Financial experience. Before joining the CRF-C, he worked at EMC as a Financial Analyst, and as a General Ledger Accountant or Supervisor in companies such as Avery Dennison & GTS.

Expert Collaborators in Data Packaging

The following experts in the area of research data packaging have offered their support to this project and are keen to collaborate with the project team throughout our evaluation of data packaging specifications and tools.

Stian Soiland-Reyes and Professor Carole Goble, eScience Lab, School of Computer Science, University of Manchester (www.researchobject.org/about/)

Jo Barratt and Paul Walsh, Open Knowledge International and Frictionless Data (www.frictionlessdata.io)

Dr. Peter Sefton, eResearch Support, University of Technology, Sydney, and maintainer of the DataCrate data packaging specification (<https://github.com/UTS-eResearch/datacrate>)

I confirm that the team members or key collaborators named above have agreed to be involved, as described, in the proposed research and are willing for their details to be included as part of this application.

Confirmed

5. Transparent decision making

Are you happy for us to share these details of your application on the Wellcome website?

Yes

6. Proposal summary

Provide an outline of what your successfully completed Open Research Fund activity will look like and what you will have achieved.

Research data are often lost or discarded at the end of a study, despite their continued value. Funders are cognisant of this loss, so researchers are increasingly being asked to prepare their data according to the **FAIR Guiding Principles** (<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>), ensuring they will be made findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. However, many researchers don't have the knowledge or skills to incorporate FAIR principles into their existing data workflows. This is a key barrier to widespread engagement with FAIR principles, and other open science practices facilitated by good data stewardship.

To help overcome this barrier, we will evaluate how **data packaging**, a promising, practical approach to FAIR data stewardship, can be incorporated into the workflows of an experienced data analysis support unit. At the end of our evaluation, we will establish a practical convention for processing and packaging research datasets and software in a manner that is teachable, reproducible, and consistent with FAIR.

By the end of the project, we will have:

- evaluated how to best incorporate candidate data packaging formats into a clinical research workflow
- estimated the costs for each method
- established the degree of metadata description and semantic modelling that is useful and achievable
- documented our investigation and experiences openly
- improved understanding of investigator needs and attitudes towards these practices
- published a practical step-by-step guide
- presented our findings to the wider research community to enable similar investigations within other disciplines and domains
- established a FAIR data service for the College of Medicine and Health at University College Cork

7. Details of proposal

Provide details of your Open Research Fund proposal, including:

- (i) the vision for your proposal, including aims, target audiences, activities;
- (ii) how your proposal will influence open research practices in your field or more broadly;
- (iii) how you will monitor and evaluate your proposal, including success indicators.

VISION, AIMS, and ACTIVITIES

We **aim** to develop a teachable, widely-applicable method for embedding FAIR principles in data workflows using **data packaging** (please see the attached figure). Thinking of data outputs as packages (or discrete research objects) puts the emphasis on bundling data, code and related artefacts in alongside the minimal metadata needed for someone else to understand and re-use them with ease and confidence. The simplicity of the approach, which often involves simply including a few additional files in an existing folder structure, transforms the daunting, abstract topic of **interoperable data stewardship** into a problem that can be more easily addressed in familiar terms using known tools.

For this project, different data packaging options will be field-tested by the **Statistics and Data Analysis Unit (SDAU)** of the Health Research Board (HRB) Clinical Research Facility Cork (CRF-C), in collaboration with the **Research and Digital Services** at the UCC Library. The SDAU (<https://crfcsdau.github.io/post/>) currently supports over 30 ongoing academic-led, patient-focused research projects in epidemiology and clinical trials. We are typically involved at every stage of these projects, but our primary contributions are in the areas of data collection, management, and analysis.

The SDAU will thus provide an ideal, “real-world” testing arena for evaluating a data packaging approach. Our volume of work will provide opportunities for testing different options, facilitate accurate costings, and allow us to survey a variety of investigators about their views on FAIR and open science. Because the research we support is so varied, ranging from small observational studies to multinational clinical trials, we will also be able to demonstrate the applicability of our findings to the wider health research community. Our expertise in working with data will help us to identify the most practical, cost-effective means of embedding FAIR principles into our established workflows, serving as a useful example for others.

Ultimately, we want to help others to bridge the gap between their existing data handling practices and the requirements of FAIR data stewardship, particularly the more esoteric challenge of ensuring minimally sufficient data interoperability.

Our aims will be met through the following activities:

- An expert meeting to selecting relevant **data packaging** options for evaluation and to establish the degree of **metadata description and semantic modelling** that is useful and achievable.
- **Modifying existing SDAU workflows** to incorporate the data packaging options.
- Hiring a FAIR Data Steward who will be tasked the the day-to-day **FAIRification** of SDAU research outputs.
- Updating existing SDAU reporting processes to facilitate **monitoring** of these changes.
- Estimating the **costs** of adding FAIRification to existing data workflows.
- Developing and deploying a **survey** on investigator needs, attitudes, and perceived barriers for open science and FAIR.
- Developing and publishing (in a variety of formats) a **best practices guide** for practical FAIR implementation using data packages.
- **Presenting our experiences** to the wider research community to enable similar investigations within other units, disciplines and domains.

INFLUENCE

The outputs of this project will provide practical guidance, empowering applied-researchers from a variety of fields to incorporate FAIR data stewardship into their daily workflows. This will be disseminated online, through workshops, formal publication, and by engagement with professional health research networks (e.g. Clinical Research Coordination Ireland, HRB Trials Methodology Research Network).

More broadly, this work will provide an important case-study to inform adoption of research data packaging approaches. Specifically, the findings will directly inform the work of several Research

Data Alliance working groups of which UCC Library is already an active member. Similarly, through direct and open engagement (e.g. improved documentation, gap analysis, issue logging, pull-requests) with the maintainers of key data packaging initiatives, our experiences will influence the development of these projects and broaden their adoption.

MONITORING

Each packaging format will be evaluated against emerging FAIR Data metrics, and in relation to the following qualitative criteria: ease of learning; ease of teaching; ease of integration with existing statistical analysis workflows; quality of existing documentation; quality of existing tooling (e.g. GUIs, software libraries).

Monitoring the effectiveness and limitations of the 'data packaging' approach when applied to actual project data is a key element of this project, including clearly demonstrating potential risks and costs. Existing SDAU workflows allow us to support a large amount of research relative to the resources available to us. We are thus risk-averse when faced with the prospect of changing them.

Impact on existing SDAU activity will be facilitated by our existing reporting procedures, both within the CRF-C, and to our funder, the HRB. We currently track a number of metrics, including the number of projects initiated, progress on these, and research outputs. We also have an existing processes for opening and closing SDAU projects, that revolves around evaluating the potential for research projects we are asked to collaborate on, clarifying research aims, and assessing how satisfied our collaborators were with the support. We will thus be able to see how the implementation of FAIR practices impact on these.

Additional information

You may submit up to two A4 pages of additional information (such as graphs, figures, tables and essential unpublished data).

Figure 1: A simplified illustration of the current SDAU workflow which implements best practices for reproducible data analysis built around the R ecosystem (e.g. tidyverse, R-markdown, etc.). The to-be workflow shows the addition of basic data annotation and packaging to this existing process which, while causing minimal disruption, dramatically improves the interoperability of the data, making it a permanent, findable, citable, accessible and reusable output of the research. (Note, this diagram is partially based on similar illustrations of reproducible workflows by Hadley Wickham)

8. Outputs management and sharing

Will the proposed research generate outputs of data, software, materials or intellectual property that hold significant value as a resource for the wider research community?	Yes
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Which approach do you intend to use to maximise the impact of your significant research outputs to improve health and benefit the wider research community?

Make research outputs available for access and re-use

Please provide an outputs management plan. Ensure this describes any significant data, software, materials or intellectual property outputs, their management, and resources required (refer to guidance).

The project will generate a number of research outputs:

- Dataset from the survey of research collaborator views on FAIR data and open science.
- Dataset of information used to estimate costings
- Minutes from expert meetings
- Updated standard operating procedures that include FAIRification of data

These outputs will be shared upon the completion of the project (1 year from the start of funding). They will be made available on an Open Science Framework project. We will promote the existence of the materials through social media, existing networks and collaborations, publication of scientific papers, and through the dissemination workshop. There will be no limits on sharing (CC-0 license). The overall project and each object will be given their own DOI.

9. Costs requested

Currency requested

Select the currency in which you wish to apply.

EUR - Euro

Salaries

Are you requesting salaries?

Yes

Salaries

Description	Total (€)
Research Data Coordinator (Admin Level V, 1.0 FT, 8 Months)	36,354

Materials and consumables

Are you requesting materials and consumables?

Yes

Materials and consumables

Description	Total (€)
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Description	Total (€)
Laptop	2,000
Consumables (paper, printer ink, etc)	500

Equipment Are you requesting equipment?	No
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Miscellaneous costs Are you requesting miscellaneous costs?	Yes
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Miscellaneous costs

Description	Total (€)
Dissemination Workshop	5,000
Collaborator travel	7,000

Justification for costs requested Provide a high-level budget breakdown and justification for costs requested.
<p>Research Data Coordinator - The main cost for the project will be salary to hire a research data coordinator. This person will be responsible for the day-to-day FAIRification of data and implementing the different data packaging options into the SDAU workflows (with supervision). By the end of the project, because we will have costed the addition of FAIR data services to our existing support, we will be able to support the post going forward from fees paid by our research collaborators. NOTE: We are not requesting support for any other salaries, as we view the proposed work as an integral part of our existing responsibilities.</p> <p>Laptop - For use by the Research Data Coordinator.</p> <p>Dissemination workshop - At the end of the project, we will host a 2 day dissemination workshop at UCC, where we will present our finalized SDAU workflows, our estimated costings per project for a FAIR data service, and our overall approach to conducting the project. The 5k budgeted will be roughly split between catering, speaker travel, renting space, and workshop materials.</p> <p>Collaborator travel - We are planning two week-long meetings for the collaborators to discuss data packaging options, view existing SDAU workflows, and plan modifications. One of these will be in Cork, and the other in Manchester. Each will involve travel and accommodation for 3-5 participants.</p>

Summary of financial support requested	
	Total (€)
Salaries / Stipends	36,354
Materials and consumables	2,500
Equipment	0
Miscellaneous other	12,000
Total	50,854